

Supplementary material to the paper: “Facilitating the comprehension of business process models for unexperienced modelers using token-based animations

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Contents

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Survey Intro

Dear Participant,

The following survey contains:

- profile questions,
- questions related to your cognitive (learning) style,
- multiple-choice questions on BPMN.

Each BPMN question contains a model, and 1 or a few animated video. **Please watch the video before answering the questions.** You can pause it, replay and adjust the speed as much as you like.

You need to answer each question before you can continue. You can go back to a previous question, if you want.

We estimate a total time of 1 hour and 30 minutes.

Good Luck!

Pre-survey

What is your age? Enter a number

What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary / third gender / other

In what domain do you already have a **bachelor's degree** (academic or professional)? (e.g. Bachelor in Finance, Business Administration, Accounting, IT, ...)

Do you already hold a master's degree?

- No, no master yet
- Yes, a master in ...

When did you learn about **process modeling** for the first time? (with BPMN or any other language (like Petri nets, Activity diagrams, ...))

- During this semester
- During the first semester of this academic year
- A few months before I started the current program
- Last academic year (2020 – 2021)
- More than 2 years ago
- Don't know it at all

Which process modeling language(s) did you learn about?
Several options are possible.

- None
- BPMN
- Petri Nets
- Activity Diagrams
- Other(s)

Approximately how many **process models** have you **read/analyzed** in the past year? (in BPMN or any other language like Petri nets, Activity diagrams, ...)

- None
- Less than 5.
- Between 5 and 10
- Between 10 and 15
- Between 15 and 20
- 20 or more.

Approximately how many **process models** have you **modeled** in the past year? (in BPMN or any other language (like Petri nets, activity diagrams, ...)) (Assisting other persons in modeling a process also counts)

- None
- Less than 5.
- Between 5 and 10
- Between 10 and 15
- Between 15 and 20
- 20 or more.

How would you rate your expertise related to **process modeling**? (in BPMN or any other language (like Petri nets, Activity diagrams, ...))

- Non-existent
- Almost non-existent
- Some knowledge I gained from a course, but with limited understanding
- Some knowledge I gained from one or several courses, with sufficient understanding
- I have good knowledge and created some conceptual models myself (via exercises or cases or in my professional life)
- I can consider myself an expert

Do you know what a 'token' means in BPMN or any other process modeling language?

- Never heard of it
- Heard of it, but don't remember what it means
- Know what it is, but don't remember the exact details
- I know quite well what tokens represent in process modeling, but never seen it in BPMN
- I know what tokens represent in BPMN

Pre-experimentation Introduction

There are 10 questions (with 1 or a few models).

We apply guess correction!

- if correct: +1

- if 'don't know': 0

- if wrong answer: $-1 / (\text{number of possible answers})$.

For example, if 3 possible answers and the wrong answer is chosen: -0.33

If you don't know the answer, you can choose that option instead of guessing.

A token is an instance or case in a process model. It is a colored circle.

Please watch the videos. They provide a process model in BPMN 2.0 notation using a token to visualize instances or cases. You can pause, replay, speed up or down as much as you like.

When you answer the questions, press next page at the bottom of the page and you will be taken to the next model.

Experimentation questions

Question 1

All the following multiple-choice questions will be rated with a guess correction.

Question 1:

Consider the following scenario carefully:

"If 'draft business requirements' is not performed within 4 weeks, the business analyst (1st lane) will notify the manager (2nd lane). The draft has to be finished before a review can be done. And obviously the review will only be performed once."

Which of the following 3 diagrams describes this scenario correctly? (Answer below)

1)

2)

3)

The scenario: "If 'draft business requirements' is not performed within 4 weeks, the business analyst (1st lane) will notify the manager (2nd lane). The draft has to be finished before a review can be done. And obviously the review will only be performed once."

Which model correctly depicts the given scenario?

- | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| 1 | 2 | 3 | I don't know |
| <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> |

Please rate this question

- | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| Very difficult | Difficult | Rather difficult | Rather easy | Easy | Very easy |
| <input type="radio"/> |

Please rate the token animations in the video:

- | | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| | Not at all | Very little | Little | To some extent | To a large extent | To a great extent |
| Were they useful? | <input type="radio"/> |
| Were they sufficient? | <input type="radio"/> |

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 2

Question 2:

Given is the following scenario:

"You feel hungry and want to order a pizza. Ordering the pizza (i.e., 'Order pizza') takes 10 minutes. After Order pizza is performed, you wait 15 minutes, if the pizza is not there, you complain and then wait for another 40 minutes. If the pizza is still not delivered then, so after you have been waiting for 55 minutes, you cancel the order."

Which diagram is correct? (Select the right answer below)

1)

2)

3)

The scenario: "You feel hungry and want to order a pizza. Ordering the pizza (i.e., 'Order pizza') takes 10 minutes. After Order pizza is performed, you wait 15 minutes, if the pizza is not there, you complain and

then wait for another 40 minutes. If the pizza is still not delivered then, so after you have been waiting for 55 minutes, you cancel the order."

Which model correctly depicts the given scenario?

Please watch the scenarios carefully to find the right answer.

- | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| 1 | 2 | 3 | I don't know |
| <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> | <input type="radio"/> |

Please rate this question

- | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| Very difficult | Difficult | Rather difficult | Rather easy | Easy | Very easy |
| <input type="radio"/> |

Please rate the token animations in the video:

- | | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| | Not at all | Very little | Little | To some extent | To a large extent | To a great extent |
| Were they useful? | <input type="radio"/> |
| Were they sufficient? | <input type="radio"/> |

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 3

Question 3

Assume the following:

You order 12 tickets for a show. 'Order ticket' takes 17 minutes, and you will receive an e-ticket before you receive an e-invoice. How many emails will you receive at the end?

Answer below.

You order 12 tickets for a show. 'Order ticket' takes 17 minutes, and you will receive an e-ticket before you receive an e-invoice. How many emails will you receive at the end?

- 0 1 2 3 I don't know
-

Please rate this question

- Very difficult Difficult Rather difficult Rather easy Easy Very easy
-

Please rate the token animations in the video:

	Not at all	Very little	Little	To some extent	To a large extent	To a great extent
Were they useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Were they sufficient?	<input type="radio"/>					

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 4

Question 4

Given is the following description:

“If the ordered item is out of stock, don't ship the order and end the order process.”

Which diagram fragment expresses this behavior?

Answer below.

1)

2)

3)

4)

"If the ordered item is out of stock, don't ship the order and end the order process."

Which diagram matches the description correctly?

- | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | I don't know |
| <input type="radio"/> |

Please rate this question

- | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| Very difficult | Difficult | Rather difficult | Rather easy | Easy | Very easy |
| <input type="radio"/> |

Please rate the token animations in the video:

- | | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| | Not at all | Very little | Little | To some extent | To a large extent | To a great extent |
| Were they useful? | <input type="radio"/> |
| Were they sufficient? | <input type="radio"/> |

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 5

Question 5

Given is the following BPMN model:

Which of the following statements is TRUE ? Please study the scenarios carefully to find the right answer.

- The model depicts that if the payment for a gold card is not received within 2 weeks, a reminder is sent and then, if the customer did not pay within 3 weeks the process is cancelled.
- The model depicts that if the payment for a gold card is not received, 2 reminders are sent. One after 2 weeks and one after 4 weeks. If the payment is not done within 7 weeks, the process is cancelled.
- The model depicts that if the payment for a gold card is not received within 4 weeks and 2 reminders, further reminders will be sent every 2 weeks forever, but the customer can pay anytime to stop the reminders and receive the gold card.
- Regardless of its meaning, the process is not correct because it is not allowed to have so many events in the 2nd event-based gateway.
- I don't know

Please rate this question

Very difficult

Difficult

Rather difficult

Rather easy

Easy

Very easy

Please rate the token animations in the video:

Not at all Very little Little To some extent To a large extent To a great extent

Were they useful?

Were they sufficient?

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 6

Question 6

Given is the following process model. Please answer the questions below. (With guess correction)

Please answer the questions below.

	Yes	No	I don't know
Can F be executed more than once for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If F is executed for an instance, can J be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If G is executed for a case, is L then always executed for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can B and J be started at the same time for a certain instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can J be executed more than once in the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If D is executed for a case, can L be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Yes No I don't know

Can E and H be completed at the same time for the same instance?

Could this model lead to a deadlock for an instance? (I.e. an improper completion, a situation where an instance is 'stuck' somewhere in the flow before reaching the end event.)

Please rate this assignment

Very difficult Difficult Rather difficult Rather easy Easy Very easy

Please rate the token animations in the video:

Not at all Very little Little To some extent To a large extent To a great extent

Were they useful?

Were they sufficient?

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 7

Question 7

Given is the following process model. Please answer the questions below.
(With guess correction)

Please answer the following questions:

	Yes	No	I don't know
If E is executed for an instance, can N be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If H is executed for an instance, can I then be executed more than once for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IF K is executed for an instance, should M also be executed for that same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can N be executed more than once in the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If C is executed for an instance, can H be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Yes	No	I don't know
If J is executed for an instance, is M then always executed for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can E and M be started (performed) at the same time for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Could this model lead to a deadlock for an instance? (I.e. an improper completion, a situation where an instance is 'stuck' somewhere in the flow before reaching the end event.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please rate this assignment

Very difficult	Difficult	Rather difficult	Rather easy	Easy	Very easy
<input type="radio"/>					

Please rate the token animations in the video:

	Not at all	Very little	Little	To some extent	To a large extent	To a great extent
Were they useful?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
Were they sufficient?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 8

Question 8

Given is the following process model. Please answer the questions below.
(With guess correction)

Please answer the following questions:

	Yes	No	I don't know
Can I be executed more than once for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If N is executed for an instance, can B be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If C is executed for an instance, is L then always executed for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can C and M be started at the same time for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can N be executed more than once in the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If L is executed for an instance, can I be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

	Yes	No	I don't know
If E is executed for an instance, is N then always executed for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can A and J be started at the same time for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Could this model lead to a deadlock for an instance? (I.e. an improper completion, a situation where an instance is 'stuck' somewhere in the flow before reaching the end event.)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please rate this assignment

Very difficult	Difficult	Rather difficult	Rather easy	Easy	Very easy
<input type="radio"/>					

Please rate the token animations in the video:

	Not at all	Very little	Little	To some extent	To a large extent	To a great extent
Were they useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Were they sufficient?	<input type="radio"/>					

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 9

Question 9

Given is the following process model. Please answer the questions below. (With guess correction)

Please answer the following questions:

	Yes	No	I don't know
Is K always executed more than once for an instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If H is executed for an instance, can J be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can D and F be started at the same time for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can N be executed more than once in the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If C is executed for an instance, can L be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If I is executed for an instance, is N then always executed for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Yes No I don't know

Can H and C be started at the same time for the same instance?

Could this model lead to a deadlock for an instance? (I.e. an improper completion, a situation where an instance is 'stuck' somewhere in the flow before reaching the end event.)

Please rate this assignment

Very difficult Difficult Rather difficult Rather easy Easy Very easy

Please rate the token animations in the video:

Not at all Very little Little To some extent To a large extent To a great extent
Were they useful?
Were they sufficient?

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Question 10

Question 10

Given is the following process model. Please answer the questions below.
(With guess correction)

Please answer the following questions:

	Yes	No	I don't know
Can E be executed more than once for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If G is executed for an instance, can E be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If A is executed for an instance, is B then always executed for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Could B and C and I be started at the same time for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can L be executed more than once in the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
If M is executed for an instance, can G be executed later on for the same instance?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Yes No I don't know

If I is executed for an instance, is L then always executed for the same instance?

Can E be executed after D for an instance?

Could this model lead to a deadlock for an instance? (I.e. an improper completion, a situation where an instance is 'stuck' somewhere in the flow before reaching the end event.)

Please rate this assignment

Very difficult	Difficult	Rather difficult	Rather easy	Easy	Very easy
<input type="radio"/>					

Please rate the token animations in the video:

	Not at all	Very little	Little	To some extent	To a large extent	To a great extent
Were they useful?	<input type="radio"/>					
Were they sufficient?	<input type="radio"/>					

Can you briefly justify your rates on usefulness and sufficiency of the animations? What is great and/or what could be improved? (optional)

Overall, how would you rate the difficulty of understanding the provided scenarios in the videos?

Very difficult	Difficult	Slightly Challenging	Not so Challenging	Easy	Very Easy
<input type="radio"/>					

Overall, how would you rate the sufficiency of the provided scenarios in the videos?

Very Insufficient	Insufficient	Slightly Insufficient	Slightly Sufficient	Sufficient	Very sufficient
<input type="radio"/>					

Given the token animations in the videos, to what extent did you actually apply them in your thinking process (mentally) to understand the models and answer the questions?

- I have not applied them to answer questions
- I applied tokens mentally to understand *SOME* models
- I applied tokens mentally to understand *MOST* models
- I applied tokens mentally to understand *ALL* models

If you applied tokens mentally, can you describe in a few sentences how you applied them.

If you applied them, what are their benefits for you?

What would be your general recommendations for teachers to improve your understanding of BPMN?

Thanking screen

We thank you for your time spent taking this survey.
Your response has been recorded.